

Title: Capturing customers behavior and predictive shelf availability

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INTRODUCTION:

The best place to know customers behavior is while he/she is shopping, this behavior is monitored today in every shopping location, but it is monitored for only security purposes, to repurpose the value acquired by the video feed, my paper presents an Idea where we will utilize a live video feed, and capture the information in series of sequences, then we use Recurrent neural network to learn from these sequences to gather information about the products and the arrangement of products during the shopping session.

AIM:

Capturing customer behavior during a shopping sequence and predicting shelf availability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Business as ABInBev having world's largest beverage distribution and production, it is very important business aspect for us to know the demand and the need of a product. So, we need to have a pair of eye, which learn product availability with firsthand information available to us.

The team here in New York took up the challenge and started gathering video feeds to learn about customer behavior. The first step to get this process going is getting the storage required for training the dataset off of the live video. Business already has a storage capability using Teradata, here we store sequence of video stream, these sequences are then hand labeled with captions based on what the analyst notices in the scene, the analyst can put multiple captions for the same frame in time. The captions are stored in the following format:

```
[{'filepath:'path/file, 'caption:' 'customer picked up a Busch 30 Pack'},...]
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The data is then divided for training purpose, during the training, the video is resized to a 240x240 frame size, and it is fed to a VGG16 model, where the SoftMax function is removed and 4208 features are extracted and fed to a Recurrent Neural Net. The captions are fed as multiple input to a Long Short Term Memory network, the network here learns the most basic connections in word appearances and test its learning on the test video sequence. We receive an output which is customer behavior during a new video sequence that is shown to the model. There is a secondary model that determines and tracks the shelf availability, whenever a product is out of stock, the region is marked in the video feed to warn about the unavailability of stock.

RESULTS:

A general prediction is made on customers action and more importantly on the brands the customer is interacting with, also a very import area of the problem is covered by cautioning the unavailability of a product to the teller as well as the out of stock situation to the producer directly.

KEYWORDS:

Customer Behavior; Shelf Availability; Deep Learning; Big Data; RNN; CNN; LSTM's.

BIOGRAPHY:

I am a Robotics Engineer with a Data Science specialization, I have previously worked with research teams in Chennai, India, where I was helping them build fully autonomous vehicles for two years and later in 2015 we went on and launched a solar capable 120 Miles long range vehicle. I am currently working as a Data Scientist at Anheuser Busch where I provide solutions in Inventory Management and Sales, and it is great to work here as there are no boundaries to problems you can solve and help the business grow.